

A STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHING PROFESSION FOR SELF FINANCED SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Cite This Article: R. Indira & Dr. K. Vellaichamy, "A Study on Attitude towards Teaching Profession for Self Financed School Teachers", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 369-371, 2018.

Abstract:

Attitudes affect both our social perception and behaviors. Attitude is a tendency which is attributed to the individual and which forms his thoughts, feelings, and behaviors about a psychological object (Kağıtçıbaşı, 1999, p.102). Attitudes are evaluation statements, either positive or negative, about objects, people or events. Attitudes express how an individual feels about something (Robbins, 1994, p. 17). Attitudes are different from opinions, values, and beliefs.

Design: Descriptive, Method: Normative, Technique: Survey

Sample: The stratified representative sample of 145 secondary grade teachers from thirty schools in Madurai district with due representation to the variables viz. Gender, Age, School Locality and Marital Status.

- Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai district is below the average level.
- Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai is independent upon Gender, Age, and Marital Status.
- Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai is dependent upon School Locality only.

Need for the Study:

Education is conceived as a powerful agency, which is instrumental in bringing about the desired changes in the social and cultural life of a nation. The whole process of education is shaped and moulded by the teachers, who play a pivotal role in any system of education. The teacher is the indispensable component of the education system. No matter how well educational or instructional objectives are established, no matter how functional the content of the subject is selected and organized, it is impossible to achieve the desired results from education unless they are performed by teachers with those objectives and insights (Sünbül, 2001, p. 224). For an educational system to achieve its objectives, it is necessary to achieve the specified objectives in classrooms, which are the sub-systems of that educational system. Attitudes are considered to be worth studying and analyzing as one of the indicators of behavior while examining the individual's behaviors. Attitudes affect both our social perception and behaviors. Attitude is a tendency which is attributed to the individual and which forms his thoughts, feelings, and behaviors about a psychological object (Kağıtçıbaşı, 1999, p.102).

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Terms and Definitions:

- Attitude towards Teaching Profession - refers to the positive or negative attitude shown towards teaching profession.
- Self-financed Schools - refers to the unaided school recognised by the Government of Tamil Nadu.
- Secondary Grade Teachers - refers to those who are handling I standard to V standard pupils in Madurai district.

Variables of the Study:

Dependent Variable:

- Attitude towards Teaching

Independent Variables:

- Gender - Male / Female
- Age - Up to 25 years / 26 years & above
- School Locality - Rural / Urban
- Marital Status - Married / Unmarried

Objectives of the Study:

- To measure the Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers.
- To find out whether there is a significant difference in Attitude towards teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in terms of the select population variables.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Each of the population variables involved in this study exerts a significant influence on attitude towards teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai district.

Studies Related to Attitude towards Teaching Profession:

Raja Winslin (2006) has done a study on attitude of trainees towards teaching profession. The aims of the study were to find out the difference in the attitude among the teacher trainees based on their gender, locality and graduation level. The study revealed that the female teacher trainees have got more favourable attitude than that of the male teacher trainees. The rural teacher trainees have got more favourable attitude than that of urban teacher trainees. Further the study revealed that the post graduate teacher trainees have got more favourable attitude than that of the graduate teacher trainees.

Ghosh S and Bairagya S (2010) have conducted a study on attitude of secondary school teachers towards teaching profession in relation to some demographic variables. The major objectives of the study were to find out the difference in the attitude among the secondary school teachers based on their gender and teaching experience. The study revealed that the female teachers have got more favourable attitude than that of male teachers. The experienced teachers have got more favourable attitude than that of the less experienced teachers.

Patchaivazhiamman J (2011) has conducted a study on teaching aptitude of trainee teachers in relation to certain selected variables. The simple random sampling technique has been utilized to select the sample. The study revealed that the male trainee teachers have got more favourable attitude than that of the female trainee teachers. The post graduate trainee teachers have got more favourable attitude than that of the under graduate trainee teachers. The government trainee teachers got more favourable attitude than that of the aided and self-finance trainee teachers. Further the study revealed that the arts stream trainee teachers have got more favourable attitude than that of the science stream trainee teachers. The teachers who got married have got more favourable attitude than that of the unmarried teachers, such a way the urban trainee teachers have got more favourable attitude than that of the rural trainee teachers.

Benjamin et al., (2011) have examined a study on attitude towards teaching profession and performance of B.Ed., trainees. The aims of the study were to find out the difference in the attitude among the B.Ed., trainees based on their gender and subject stream. The study revealed that the female B.Ed., trainees have got more attitude than that of the male B.Ed., trainees. The science stream B.Ed., trainees have got more favourable attitude than that of the arts stream B.Ed., trainees.

Methodology-In-Brief:

Design: Descriptive, Method: Normative, Technique: Survey

Sample:

The stratified representative sample of 145 secondary grade teachers from thirty schools in Madurai district with due representation to the variables viz. Gender, Age, School Locality and Marital Status.

Tool Used:

- General Information Sheet
- Attitude towards Teaching Scale developed by Marcy Abraham (2011).

Statistical Technique Used:

‘ t ’ test between the means of large independent samples was worked out.

Results and Discussions:

The empirical average of attitude towards teaching among private school secondary grade teachers is found to be 14.23, while the theoretical average is 18 only. Hence the attitude towards teaching among private school secondary grade teachers is found to be below the average level.

Table 1: Results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai district: Population Variables – Wise.

S.No	Variable	Sub-Variable	No. of Students	Mean	Standard Deviation	‘t’ value	Significance Level at 0.05
1.	Gender	Male	65	15.55	6.73	2.327	S
		Female	80	13.15	5.45		
2.	Age	Up to 25 years	96	13.38	5.67	-2.243	S
		26 & above years	49	15.89	6.75		
3.	School Locality	Rural	105	13.75	6.01	-1.470	NS
		Urban	40	15.48	6.42		
4.	Marital Status	Married	79	15.53	6.53	2.916	S
		Unmarried	66	12.67	5.29		

- NS - Denotes Not Significant
- S - Denotes Significant

Attitude towards Teaching and Gender:

The calculated 't' value (2.327) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in attitude towards teaching of male and female private school secondary grade teachers.

Attitude towards Teaching and Age:

The calculated 't' value (-2.243) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in attitude towards teaching of up to 25 years age and 26 & above years private school secondary grade teachers.

Attitude towards Teaching and School Locality:

The calculated 't' value (-1.470) is lower than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference in attitude towards teaching of rural and urban school locality of private school secondary grade teachers.

Attitude towards Teaching and Marital Status:

The calculated 't' value (2.916) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in attitude towards teaching of married and unmarried private school secondary grade teachers.

Conclusions:

The major conclusions emerged out of the study are presented below:

- Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai district is below the average level.
- Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai is independent upon Gender, Age, and Marital Status.
- Attitude towards Teaching among private school secondary grade teachers in Madurai is dependent upon School Locality only.

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